

End-to-End Network Slice Stitching using Blockchain-based Peer-to-Peer Network Slice Managers and Transport SDN Controllers

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Abstract: This paper presents and experimentally validates a Blockchain-based architecture to manage End-to-End Network Slice Deployment by stitching Network Slice Subnets in edge/cloud computing domains connected through packet/optical transport networks domains managed by different operators. © 2021 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

Nowadays, the implementation of networks for 5G services and beyond aim for a distribution of the resources around the infrastructure. All computing resources are placed using the concepts of Mobile Edge Computing (MEC) and cloud computing in the edge and core networks, respectively. These resources are interconnected with multiple packet and/or optical transport networks. Due to this resource distribution, the overall infrastructure might be organised in segments, each owned by a different operator. As each operator has its own interests, having a centralized solution to manage End-to-End (E2E) service deployments might be difficult to apply. To solve it, distributed and secure solutions are necessary to allow all the operators to keep their independence while collaborating among them. Distribute Ledger Technologies (DLT) is one of the possible tools to reach the previous objective. The most known example of DLT is Blockchain [1]. It gives the possibility to change the management of network resources from a centralized point of view, with an element on top controlling all the E2E actions, to a distributed system in which the different domains share their local resources and manage the E2E services by interacting among them. In addition to a security aspect as important as the avoidance of central point of failure, Blockchain may help the trustworthiness among different operator domains.

Due to the co-existence of different services being deployed over the same physical infrastructure and for all of these services to have their specific requirements fulfilled, the use of Network Function Virtualization (NFV) and Network Slicing becomes necessary. Having an NFV Infrastructure (NFVI) with a set of NFVI points-of-presence (NFVI-POPs) where operators have computation, storage and networking resources together with Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) allows to offer different types of network services. Due to the specific verticals requirements and the fact that they must co-exist over the same infrastructure, Network Slicing was designed as a 5G requirement to create parallel virtual logical networks (i.e., a composition of network services and their VNFs), each dedicated to a vertical service. E2E network slices must be composed of Network Slice Subnets (NSSs) deployed at the computing domains (MEC or cloud infrastructure), and they need to be stitched [2] (i.e., interconnected) across transport network domains.

This paper aims to present a Blockchain-based architecture to manage the deployment of E2E Network Slices by stitching their components (i.e., NSS) across transport network domains (both optical and packet-based) and avoid the central point of failure of having a single entity managing all the E2E actions. The Blockchain network is composed by a set of Network Slice Managers (NSM) providing NSSs in the MEC/cloud computing domains, and transport Software-Defined Network (SDN) controllers in the transport domain providing connectivity services (CSs). Compared to our previous work [3,4], the novelty is the capability to stitch the computing resources of two NSSs placed in different domains thanks to the introduction of a new component of transport SDN controllers that allows them to participate in the Blockchain.

2. Blockchain-based proposed architecture

The designed Blockchain-based Management and Orchestration (MANO) architecture (Fig.1-A) aims to remove the element on top (e.g., E2E orchestrator/controller/manager) of hierarchical architectures with the complete view across the multiple domains. In its place, the objective is to make use of a Blockchain network that allows computing and transport domains to become a peer of the Blockchain network and, finally, to share their domain information (i.e., per-domain NSSs and CSs) among them in a trustworthy way. Blockchain was designed to be a transparent and public way to share information among peers, but due to the fact that the proposed architecture is thought to be used by operators, a certain level of access restriction is necessary. For this reason, the proposed Blockchain-based MANO architecture aims to be considered as a Permissioned Distributed Ledger (PDL).

Fig.1-A shows the Blockchain-based MANO architecture, later implemented in the ADRENALINE testbed. The proposed Blockchain-based architecture has two types of peers called "PDL-NSM" or "PDL-SDN" depending

Fig. 1. Blockchain-based MANO Architecture implementation in the ADRENALINE testbed (A), Blockchain-based E2E Network Slice deployment workflow (B)

on the type of resources (i.e., NSSs or CSs) that each domain manages. The PDL-NSM is composed with the PDL-slicing manager and the NSM modules. The PDL-slicing manager is responsible for the distribution of the available NSSs from its local NSM with the other PDL-modules, to keep the information of other domain NSSs and, finally, it is in charge of initiating and managing the E2E Network Slices deployment procedure by interacting with its local NSM and the external ones through the PDL-slicing manager in other domains. The NSM in the bottom of the PDL-NSM is in charge of managing the deployment of local network slices (i.e., NSSs in the E2E Network Slice) by interacting with the NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) below and its associated Virtual Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) and the local SDN Controllers. Similarly to the PDL-NSM, the PDL-SDN is composed of two modules: the "PDL-transport manager" is in charge of taking the ONF Transport API (T-API) [5] context offered by the local Transport SDN Controller and distribute it to the other Blockchain peers. When a context is added or updated, all the peers will keep that information in their local Blockchain to update their vision of all the transport domains involved and their interconnections. Additionally, the PDL-transport manager forwards any CS request affecting its domain to the underlying Transport SDN Controller, so this can execute the corresponding CS action in its domain.

The architecture described allows all computing domains to manage E2E Network Slice deployments. As Fig. 1-B shows, only the PDL-slicing elements are able to start the process with a request from the Domain OSS/BSS (1). Then, the PDL-slicing manager requests NSSs deployment; on the one hand, to its local NSM (2) that manages their deployment with the NFVO below (3) and, on the other hand, if the NSS belongs to another domain, it distributes the requests to all the peers in the Blockchain (4-5). Only the owner (4) of the requested NSS will forward the request to its associated NSM (6) and acknowledge the NSS ownership (7). While the second action is done, the associated NSM manages the NSS deployment with the NFVO below (8). At this point the PDL-slicing manager managing the E2E deployment must wait until all the NSSs are deployed. On the one hand, it checks the local NSSs with its NSM and, once it is deployed, updates the E2E Network Slice information (9). On the other hand, for the NSSs from other domains, it must wait until a transaction arrives (11,12). The transaction is originated when the NSM in another domain finishes its NSS deployment and informs its PDL-slicing manager about it (10). The PDL-slicing manager distributes the transaction to all the peers (11,12) and only the original requester keeps it (12) and acknowledges (13) its reception. Once all the NSSs are ready, the PDL-slicing manager starts stitching action. First, it computes the path for each pair of interconnected NSSs and generates a list of CS (14). Based on the list, it distributes a transaction per each CS (15,16) to all the peers but only the PDL-transport manager with the ownership will take it (16), forward it to its associated Transport SDN Controller (17) and acknowledge its reception. Meanwhile, the Transport SDN Controller configures the CS (18). Once a CS is ready, the PDL-transport manager is informed (20) and then it generates another transaction for all the other peers (21,22). Again, only the CS requester will take it (21), and confirm its reception (23). Finally, once all the CS are ready and the NSSs stitched, the PDL-slicing manager updates the E2E NSI and informs about its completeness.

3. Experimental Validation

Fig. 2. Deployment Time Values Graph (A), and Total Deployment Time CDF (B).

To experimentally validate the presented architecture, we implemented it in our ADRENALINE testbed [6] as Fig.1-A shows. The Blockchain network is based on Ethereum due to its capability of using smart contracts and its faster block generation procedure (faster than e.g. Bitcoin). The testbed has four domains: an edge and cloud computing domains, both with its PDL-NSM module associated to a SONATA Service Platform (which has a NSM and a NFVO) and its VIMs and SDN controllers. In parallel, both packet and optical transport networks have their PDL-SDN associated to a TAPI-enabled Transport SDN controller [7].

To study the influence of Blockchain, an E2E Network Slice composed by two NSSs stitched with two uni-directional CSs through the optical transport network was designed. One NSS with a single network service in the Edge-DC 2 and the other NSS with two network services in the Core-DC. Before any deployment, the NSSs information and the SDN controller (optical and packet) transport contexts were distributed to all the Blockchain peers. Then, it was possible to request E2E Network Slices from any computing domain.

A set of tests was done to get the time values for the different actions involved in the E2E deployment: the computing (i.e., NSSs) deployment, the networking (i.e., both directions CSs) deployment and the Blockchain transactions. Analyzing the results in Fig.2-A, the Blockchain actions influence on the total E2E deployment time is very low. Comparing the mean time values between the Blockchain (4.51s) and the total E2E deployment actions (202.28s), the Blockchain time is a 2.23% because most of the E2E deployment time belong to the computing deployments (191.6s for the cloud NSS). Instead, the time to stitch the NSSs (4.08s) is similar to the Blockchain actions time (4.51s). Fig.2-B presents the cumulative distribution function (CDF) for the total E2E deployment time which shows that long time E2E deployments (219.2s) have higher probabilities (89.3%) to occur. Comparing the lowest time obtained (179s) with the Blockchain actions mean time (4.51s), the increment of time is a 2.55%. So, the percentage will reduce for longer E2E deployments.

4. Conclusions

The presented Blockchain-based MANO architecture allows a new collaborative methodology to deploy E2E Network Slices on a multi-operator infrastructure while maintaining their domain independence. Based on the results presented, a new way to manage computing resources across transport networks is feasible.

Acknowledgments

Work supported by the Spanish project AURORAS (RTI2018-099178-B-I00), the EC H2020 INSPIRE5G-plus (762055) and TeraFlow (101015857) projects.

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